

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF DIFFERENT 3D WEAVING PROCESSES, MACHINES AND PRODUCTS

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SUMMARY

Comparative analysis of various methods of manufacturing 3D woven preforms for composites shows that the differences in 3D weaving processes and machines determine the differences in reinforcement architectures. Those differences, in turn, make significant effect on the in-plane mechanical properties of manufactured composites. A comparison of fiber architectures and mechanical properties of 3D non-crimp and 3D interlock weave composites illustrates the revealed effects.

Keywords: Textile Composites, 3D Weaving, Manufacturing, Mechanical Properties

INTRODUCTION

The properties of any composite do not only depend on the reinforcing fibers and matrix materials, but also on the geometrical arrangement of the fibers (the fiber architecture). If the reinforcing fibers are aligned, the resulting composite is generally highly anisotropic with respect to modulus, strength, thermal expansion and other characteristics. By lamination and the proper choice of fiber orientations in the different directions, a wide range of mechanical and physical properties may be designed and optimized. However, properties of traditional laminates can be varied, from ply to ply, only in the in-plane directions. In the through-thickness direction they are typically very poor, and the presence of weak, resin-rich interfaces between the reinforced plies cause delamination as the most common, and most difficult to defeat, failure mode of these materials. This sets severe limitations on the use of 2-D reinforced laminated composites in many applications. Numerous examples of this kind are documented in literature (delamination and buckling of thick-walled filament wound tubes, barely visible delamination in aircraft wing caused by accidental impact, laminated stiffeners suffering from premature delamination initiated in the “noodle region” are among most notorious examples). Furthermore, the through-thickness coefficient of thermal expansion in 2-D laminates is generally higher than the in-plane ones, which is a

serious drawback in applications requiring dimensional stability, such as antennas and communications gear in spacecrafts. Several types of technological processes and machines have been developed to produce composites with enhanced through thickness properties. All of them are based on two groups of ideas: (i) add some “secondary” fiber reinforcement in the direction perpendicular to the “primary”, in-plane reinforcement and (ii) re-direct some of the primary fibers to the secondary reinforcement direction. Most famous approaches of the first kind are stitching and Z-pinning, while 3D weaving, 3D braiding and 3D knitting belong to the second kind.

Each of these methods possess its inherent advantages and disadvantages, and it is always a difficult dilemma to choose one vs. the others for each particular application. For example, stitching or Z-pinning is an additional manufacturing step, which may not only cause significant damage of the in-plane fibers and thus affect the primary properties of composite, but it also increases time and cost of the manufacturing cycle and requires additional equipment. 3D interlock weaving re-directs part of the warp yarns to serve as out-of-plane reinforcement, which reduces the in-plane fiber volume fraction and creates inevitable crimp and waviness in the primary reinforcement. 3D non-crimp orthogonal weaving requires considerable spaces for insertion of the third set of fibers, so-called Z-fibers, which are incorporated during weaving in the through-thickness direction; their presence reduces the in-plane fiber volume fraction and respective composite properties. 3D braiding is characterized by a highly interlaced fiber architecture which, again, creates serious obstacles to achieving high primary properties of the composites. 3D warp knitting (a.k.a. stitch bonding) provide so-called “no-crimp fabrics”, which typically contain very thin and weak polymeric stitching threads; they do not add considerably to the out-of-plane mechanical properties. In all of these cases, composites engineer or designer faces one and the same issue: how to determine acceptable trade-off between reducing the level of primary properties and, simultaneously, raising the level of secondary ones? Paper [1] provides a detailed discussion of this issue with some practical recommendations for the case of 3D orthogonal weaving.

In the present paper we will focus on 3D weaving. Our principal objective here is to relate resulting properties of the composites, made with different types of 3D woven preforms, to the origins of their reinforcement. And those origins are, of course, specific textile processes and machines used for the preform manufacturing. No one would probably dispute the point that it is hardly possible to understand, qualify and quantify properties and predict structural performance of textile composite products without profound knowledge of their reinforcement architectures. And it seems obvious that gaining such a knowledge is hardly possible without learning essential aspects of respective textile processing methods and equipment. For example, how to understand why some “3D woven composite” has surprisingly low in-plane stiffness and strength, without not only knowing how the preform looks but also how it was made? How to build a continuous chain of knowledge from the first link, which is selection of specific

3D weaving machine, to establishing its set up parameters, to determination of the fiber placement in dry preform, to the reinforcement architecture in composite product, and finally to its properties and in-service performance characteristics? Certain aspects of this huge but essential problem have been considered in review paper [2]. This paper addresses some other aspects, which look very important from these authors' perspective.

FROM 2D TO 3D WEAVING: THE PRINCIPLES

Traditional 2D weaving has been around for thousands of years and is a relatively high-speed economical process. Figure 1 illustrates the main functions of weaving, namely shedding, filling insertion, and beat-up. The interlacing between the warp (longitudinal or 0° direction) yarns and filling (cross or 90° direction) yarns forms the fabric. However, because of this interlacing, woven fabrics have an inherent waviness or crimp in the interlaced yarns, and this is undesirable for maximum composite properties.

Figure 1. The main functions of conventional 2D weaving [3].

Figure 2 shows the arrangement of the warp, filling, and fabric on the weaving apparatus, referred to as loom or weaving machine, depending on the extent of engineering control on the operating mechanisms [3]. It is important to note that in order to move the warp sheets up and down to perform the shedding function as shown in Figure 2a; each warp end has to be drawn through a heddle eye. This is significant in affecting the design of the fabric and the extent of abrasion the yarn is subjected to during weaving. In Figure 2b, the warp passes through the dents of the reed, which actuates the beat-up action. The movement of the reed presents another source of abrasion against the warp yarns. Figure 2c shows the flow of material on the loom. In most cases, the warp supply is in the form a beam. However, in special cases, such as zero twist glass rovings, weaving is normally better from a creel.

Multilayer woven fabrics, which are often referred to as three-dimensional, or 3D woven fabrics, have been used for a long time in industrial applications, particularly in belting, webbing, and paper-making fabrics. These fabrics are composed of several series of warp yarns and filling (a.k.a. weft) yarns that form distinct layers, one above the other [4]. The fabrics can be woven as thick dense structure or with a space between

layers (core fabrics). The layers can be bound together by interlacing warp ends in the structure with the filling of adjacent layers, which is referred to as angle interlock 3D weaving, see Figure 3a. When the warp ends interlace with the face and back filling layers, it is referred to as warp interlock 3D weaving, see Figure 3b. As can be seen, both architectures have substantial level of crimp.

Figure 2. Warp fiber and fabric arrangement on the 2D weaving loom [3].

Figure 3. Fiber architectures in 3D Interlock weaves [5].

Inserting wadding or stuffing yarns, which remain straight in the fabric, contribute fully to stiffness and strength in the longitudinal fabric direction. Yarns that interlace between the face and bottom layers as binding yarns, contribute only partially to the stiffness and strength in that direction. If the (binding or Z) yarns interlace with the face and back layers in a vertical configuration, the structure is referred to as orthogonal weave. In this case, the binding yarns contribute mainly to the stiffness and strength in the through-thickness direction. One of the problems of weaving these structures on traditional 2D weaving machines is the difficulty in maintaining proper stacking of the filling yarns in the different layers.

3D WEAVING DEVICES AND MACHINES

Traditional weaving machines adapt well to making multilayer panels of somewhat limited thickness by building up the layers one pick at a time, which reduces the productivity of these machines, even at high weaving speeds. These machines can be used with cam, dobby, or Jacquard shedding mechanisms. One of the drawbacks of weaving advanced fibers on this type of machines is the extent of the fiber damage caused by the moving machine parts. This is due to all the warp ends have to be drawn through the heddles on the harness frames of the shedding mechanism, as shown in Figure 4. All the harnesses have to be moved up and down during every weaving cycle, even if the design does not require them to move. This action subjects all the warp ends to substantial degree of abrasion between the ends and the heddles, as well as between the ends in the different warp layers. The extent of the fiber damage can be severe, as reported in works [6-8]. This may be a serious limiting factor in terms of machine speed (the imparted damage obviously increases with machine operating at higher speeds), which in turn negatively affects the economics of such 3D weaving. Another drawback of weaving multilayer fabrics on 2D weaving machines is the presence of high level of interlacing leading to a high degree of fiber crimp or waviness. These factors are detrimental to the properties of the composites since the crimped fibers only contribute partially to the composite stiffness and strength. 3TEX has developed a process for modifying traditional 2D weaving machines to weave 3D orthogonal fabrics at high speed with reduced levels of crimp [9].

Figure 4. Warp arrangement for weaving multilayer fabric on 2D weaving machine.

Another development that suffers from the crimp and fiber damage problems is the so-called “first ever 3D-weaving process” described in [10]; this features dual-directional shedding operations referred to as “linear-linear” and “linear-angular”. The shedding operation alternately displaces the grid-like arranged warp yarns Z (disposed in accordance with cross-sectional profile to be produced) to enable creation of multiple sheds in the thickness and width directions. Two mutually perpendicular sets of

corresponding vertical wefts Y and horizontal wefts X (Figure 5) are inserted into the created sheds. The warps Z, therefore, interlace with the sets of vertical Y and horizontal X wefts, thus creating an interlaced woven 3D fabric, see Figure 5. Due to the interlacing, the resulting structure has crimped fibers in all three directions, which would be detrimental for potential applications of this type of fabric as a composite reinforcement. Alan Prichard noted in [11] that “crimped fibers are dead-weight”. Furthermore, the weaving concept proposed in [10] imposes significant limitations on the fabric width and thickness. If the process is carried out mechanically at any reasonable speed, which appears uncertain to date, it would create substantial fiber damage with the use of advanced fibers, such as glass, carbon, ceramic, etc. Since the process can only handle 60 fiber tows in each of the horizontal and vertical directions, the preform dimensions determine the fiber volume fractions. Achieving high fiber volume fractions by this method is questionable for realistic size components.

Figure 5. Schematic of 3D woven fabric produced by method [10].

Weaving very thick and complex three-dimensional textile structures have required the development of specialized 3D devices and weaving machines [12]. They incorporate variations in fiber feed, yarn tensioning, beat-up, and take-up mechanisms. A fully automated computer controlled 3D weaving process with simultaneous multiple filling insertions, has been developed at North Carolina State University, College of Textiles [13]. Figure 6 shows the simultaneous insertion of 10 filling yarns. This process is inherently a three-dimensional one, from the onset. It does not involve the building up of the fabric layers in through thickness direction and, consequently, it cannot use and does not use any of the traditional 2D weaving equipment. Rather, a unit of thick non-crimp multilayered fabric is formed during each weaving cycle. The essence of the innovation [13] centers on this simultaneous multiple filling yarn insertions from one or both sides of the fabric. 3TEX, Inc. has been further developing and commercializing this patented technology since 1998, currently under the trademark, 3WEAVE®. Besides aforementioned automated use of multiple filling yarn insertion in a single weaving cycle, this 3D weaving approach enables for producing certain complex net-shaped preforms, like “I”, “T”, “II”, “H”, “□”, as well as integral truss core and pile structures. It also allows for a broad variation of the Z-directional fiber volume content in order to optimize the 3D reinforcement architecture in composite for specific

applications. Another benefit provided by this technology is virtually unlimited hybridization opportunities by using different fiber materials and yarn sizes in the preform. Each warp yarn layer, each filling yarn layer, and each of the two Z yarn layers can be individualized in terms of the fiber material used and the yarn size.

Figure 6. Simultaneous insertion of filling yarns on 3TEX non-crimp weaving machine.

In addition to these advances, 3WEAVE[®] preforms have zero internal fiber crimp in the warp- and weft-directional yarns, because there is no interlacing between the layers of these yarns, and proper tension control is applied to keep them straight. The warp ends are not required to be drawn through the heddles of the shedding mechanism, leading to very much reduced fiber damage in the weaving process. Only the Z fibers have to be moved up and down, thus they have to be drawn into the heddles. Owing to the simultaneous insertion of all filling yarns, the machine productivity (in terms of the product volume, not length) can be fairly high even at low speed.

Preforms made by the process provide several important advantages in composites fabrication. Their most obvious advantage appears in manufacturing thick composites, particularly in lowering composites fabrication costs due to a dramatically reduced labor time, when multiple layers of 2D fabric plies are replaced by one or few plies of 3WEAVE[®] providing same required thickness in a composite structure.

A COMPARISON OF DIFFERENT 3D WOVEN PREFORMS

3D woven fabrics (particularly, interlock weaves), manufactured on essentially 2D weaving devices and machines, have been studied intensively since the late 1990s, see [14-17] for example, and their extensive studies continue now. Most of the earlier applications required using high temperature carbon and ceramic matrices, and it was not the primary design requirement to achieve high fiber volume fractions, keep in-plane yarns as straight and aligned as possible, and maximize in-plane stiffness and strength. Due to these circumstances, highly crimped, wavy and irregular fabric architectures, as the ones illustrated in Figure 7, were usually accepted. In spite of significant theoretical effort in modeling these fabrics, it was hard to reliably predict

elastic and strength properties of their composites without involvement of probabilistic and stochastic methods, like in [18-21]. High variability and randomness of these 3D woven fabric architectures had reflected on composite properties. The fabric geometry model, shown in left image of Figure 7, has been introduced in 1994; it is still used by many authors as a representative schematic of “3D woven fabric architecture”.

Figure 7. Schematic of the deformation of a stuffer and filler near and extremum of a warp weaver (left). Typical distortions of (a) stuffers and (b) fillers in the heavily compacted composite *h-L-1* (right) [15].

The fabric geometry model and the cross section images shown in Figure 7 have been introduced in 1994, and they are still used by many authors as a representative model of “3D woven fabric architecture”. In contrast to that, the other two images, shown in Figure 8, correspond to a thick carbon fiber-epoxy matrix composite reinforced with a non-crimp 3D orthogonal woven preform manufactured on one of 3TEX’s machines. They are radically different from what is seen in Figure 7 - no crimp, no waviness, and no irregularities seen even after these preforms were converted into a composite.

Figure 8. Carbon-epoxy 3D non-crimp weave composite cross sections: Warp-Z (left) and Fill-Z (right).

PROPERTIES OF DIFFERENT 3D WOVEN COMPOSITES

Not to a surprise, using radically different 3D weaving processes and machines results in very different fiber architectures of 3D woven preforms and, consequently, in very different properties of the composites made thereof. The very first comparative experimental studies of 3D interlock weave vs. 3D non-crimp weave composites [22, 23] had convincingly validated this point. Carbon fiber/epoxy composites were

fabricated using three different fabric preform types, at Messerschmitt-Bolkow-Blohm (MBB) Central Laboratories, Munich, Germany. The preforms were: a stack of 2D woven fabrics, a single-ply “conventional” 3D warp interlock weave, and a single-ply non-crimp 3D orthogonal weave produced at NCSU on their novel machine. The laminated 2D weave composite samples were fabricated using the “prepreg technique”. The 3D woven composite samples were manufactured by filling in the first step the preform placed in a mould by liquid epoxy resin film under vacuum, then consolidating it in the second step in an autoclave. All three composite samples had comparable thickness near 6 mm. The total fiber volume fraction in both 3D weave reinforced composites was very close, around 50%.

Mechanical tests have been conducted at MBB lab for tension, compression, interlaminar strength, and compression after impact. Experimental results were expressed as the ratios of mechanical properties of 3D interlock weave composite and 3D non-crimp weave composite to the “baseline” 2D weave laminate. The obtained ratios for the case of interlock weave composite: tensile modulus 0.74 in warp and 0.88 in weft, tensile strength 0.67 in warp and 0.62 in weft, and compressive strength 0.56 in warp and 0.74 in weft. At the same time, the respective ratios for the case of non-crimp weave composite showed the following values: tensile modulus 1.11 in warp and 0.95 in weft, tensile strength 1.10 in warp and 1.02 in weft, and compressive strength 1.06 in warp and 0.99 in weft. The conclusion was that while the 3D interlock weave composite is much inferior for these properties vs. 2D weave laminate, the 3D non-crimp weave composite is absolutely competitive with the 2D weave laminate, even showing some higher properties. When comparing these two 3D weave reinforced composites, the respective ratios of the non-crimp weave composite to the interlock weave composite properties are: for tensile modulus 1.50 in warp and 1.08 in weft, for tensile strength 1.64 in warp and 1.64 in weft, and for compressive strength 1.89 in warp and 1.34 in weft.

These experimental results convincingly demonstrate that without making distinction between two major types of 3D woven preforms, it makes little sense talking about mechanical properties of some “generic 3D woven composites”. Different textile processes and machines may produce very different 3D woven preform with very different fiber architectures, and those result in very different composites.

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